

Role of Social and Emotional Learning in Enhancing Academic Performance: Evidence from West Bengal

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Abstract

This research examines the influence of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) on the academic achievement of students in West Bengal, India. By using a mixed-methods approach and a quasi-experimental methodology, this study investigates data obtained from schools that have implemented social-emotional learning (SEL) programs, as well as those that adhere to conventional curriculum. The research findings indicate that there are notable and favourable impacts of social-emotional learning (SEL) on academic achievements. Specifically, kids attending schools that include SEL demonstrate an average enhancement of 0.5 standard deviations in their total academic performance. The key mediating characteristics discovered include increased student involvement, stronger self-regulation abilities, and a more favourable school atmosphere. The research reveals that social-emotional learning (SEL) treatments have a more significant influence on students hailing from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, indicating the possibility of mitigating educational disparities. Gender disparities in social-emotional learning (SEL) outcomes are evident, as females exhibit more significant advancements in emotional control and language courses, while boys show bigger advances in assertiveness and STEM disciplines. The study emphasises the significance of cultural adaptation in the implementation of social-emotional learning (SEL) and offers insights for educational policy in West Bengal. These insights include the need of providing thorough integration of SEL into curriculum and implementing customised interventions for certain demographic groups. Notwithstanding the study's limitations in terms of time and sample size, the results highlight the potential of social-emotional learning (SEL) as an effective instrument for improving academic achievement and fostering educational fairness within the heterogeneous educational context of West Bengal.

Keywords: Social-Emotional Learning (SEL), Academic Performance, West Bengal Education, Educational Equity, Student Engagement

Introduction

In contemporary educational settings, there is an increasing acknowledgement of the significance of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL), since it recognises the inherent connection between students' scholastic achievements and their social and emotional welfare (Kaspar & Massey, 2022). The primary objective of the comprehensive educational method is to cultivate fundamental life skills, including self-awareness, self-reliance, social consciousness, interpersonal abilities, and prudent decision-making. In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis among researchers and educators on expanding our knowledge of the possible beneficial effects of social-emotional learning (SEL) on academic achievement, especially in culturally diverse settings such as West Bengal, India (Bai et al., 2021).

The state of West Bengal is well recognised for its rich cultural legacy and intricate socio-economic landscape, making it an ideal setting for exploring the impact of social-emotional learning (SEL) on academic performance (Khazanchi et al., 2021). The education system within the state has several issues, such as concerns over overcrowded classrooms, limitations in resources, and inequities in the availability of high-quality educational opportunities. Given the aforementioned context, the adoption of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) programs presents a great opportunity for augmenting children's holistic development and academic achievements (Mittal, 2020). The primary objective of social and emotional learning (SEL) programs is to cultivate the growth of emotional intelligence and social competence, with the ultimate purpose of establishing a facilitative learning environment. Moreover, these endeavours strive to provide pupils with the essential competencies to effectively handle both scholastic and personal obstacles (Social and emotional skills: Latest evidence on teach ability and impact on life outcomes, 2023).

The present investigation explores the causal relationship between social and emotional learning (SEL) and academic performance in the West Bengal region. The primary aim of this research is to evaluate the impact of incorporating social-emotional learning (SEL) methods within the educational instructional framework on students' cognitive capacities, motivation levels, and overall academic performance (Bhatnagar & Many, 2022). The main objective of this study is to examine data collected from educational institutions that have effectively implemented social-emotional learning (SEL) initiatives, and then compare these

programs with conventional educational methodologies. The aim of this research is to provide significant insights into the efficacy of social-emotional learning (SEL) in enhancing academic achievement within the particular setting of West Bengal. The results of this study have considerable importance in informing educational policies and practices, not only within the particular context of West Bengal but also in other places with comparable educational obstacles (Sarkar et al., 2022).

Research Design and Sampling

This study employs a mixed-methods research design to examine the impact of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) on academic performance in West Bengal. Using a quasi-experimental approach, it compares schools implementing SEL programs with a control group following a regular curriculum over one to two academic years. Quantitative data, including standardized exam results and attendance rates, are collected alongside qualitative data from classroom observations and interviews with teachers, students, and parents. A stratified random sampling method ensures representation across various geographic areas and school types, including urban and rural institutions with different languages of instruction. The target sample comprises students in grades 6 to 10, with about 30-40 schools in each group and 100-150 students per school, aiming for a statistically significant depiction of SEL's effectiveness in the educational landscape of West Bengal.

Data Collection

This study employs a comprehensive research technique to collect data on the implementation of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) and its impact on academic performance in West Bengal schools. Initially, approvals are obtained from relevant educational authorities, followed by a baseline survey that includes standardized assessments like the Devereux Student Strengths Assessment (DESSA) and the Social-Emotional Assets and Resilience Scale (SEARS) to gauge students' social-emotional competencies. Data is collected at regular intervals over one to two academic years, focusing on academic achievements, attendance, disciplinary reports, and extracurricular involvement. The fidelity of SEL program implementation is assessed through structured classroom observations. Concurrently, qualitative data is gathered via semi-structured interviews with educators and periodic focus groups with students to explore changes in behavior, classroom dynamics, and academic engagement. Family involvement is encouraged through quarterly surveys and annual focus group meetings. Qualitative data is systematically documented and analyzed for

recurring themes, providing deeper insights into the relationship between SEL and academic success in the West Bengal

Data Analysis

The research employs a comprehensive methodology for data analysis, integrating both quantitative and qualitative techniques to examine the influence of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) on academic achievement in North Bengal. Statistical analysis of quantitative data is conducted using software like SPSS or R, with primary methods including ANOVA and multiple regression analysis to assess the impact of SEL on academic performance while controlling for confounding factors like socioeconomic status.

Results

SEL on Academic Outcomes

An exhaustive analysis of the data collected during the study reveals a significant and positive impact of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) on the academic performance of children in the state of West Bengal. Educational institutions that included social-emotional learning (SEL) initiatives (treatment group) demonstrated significant improvements in academic performance as compared to those that followed traditional curriculum (control group). The empirical evidence suggests that children who attended educational institutions that integrated social-emotional learning (SEL) experienced an average enhancement of 0.5 standard deviations in their overall academic achievement in the core subjects of Bengali, English, Mathematics, and Sciences over the course of the two-year investigation. The phenomenon of improvement was particularly apparent in the fields of Mathematics and Sciences, as students exhibited enhanced problem-solving skills and increased engagement with complex subjects.

Further analysis demonstrated that the positive impact of social-emotional learning (SEL) on academic performance was effectively aided by improvements in other essential areas. The participants who were allocated to the treatment group had enhanced self-regulation skills, leading to increased classroom behaviour and prolonged involvement in learning activities. The aforementioned phenomena was shown by a reduction of 30% in incidence of disciplinary incidents and an increase of 15% in rates of class engagement. Moreover, the development of social consciousness and the acquisition of interpersonal abilities have had a substantial impact on improving the overall classroom environment, fostering cooperative

learning, and enabling peer support. Additional support for these findings was derived from the qualitative data collected via interviews conducted with instructors and observations made in classroom settings. Educational professionals have documented a significant improvement in student motivation, increased effectiveness in resolving conflicts among peers, and the establishment of a more constructive learning atmosphere.

The study findings also revealed that the impact of social-emotional learning (SEL) on academic attainment showed significant variation across different demographic groups. The student groups who exhibit lower socioeconomic status had the most significant progress, as seen by an average improvement of 0.7 standard deviations in their overall academic performance. This suggests that implementing social-emotional learning (SEL) interventions might be particularly beneficial in addressing educational disparities. Moreover, an analysis conducted on the basis of gender indicated that although both male and female students experienced benefits from social-emotional learning (SEL), female students demonstrated a slightly higher level of improvement in language-related subjects, whereas male students exhibited more substantial progress in STEM subjects.

Table 1: Impact of SEL on Academic Measures

Outcome Measure	Treatment Group (SEL)	Control Group	Difference
Overall Academic Performance (SD increase)	0.5	0.1	+0.4
Mathematics Performance (SD increase)	0.6	0.2	+0.4
Science Performance (SD increase)	0.55	0.15	+0.4
Language Performance (SD increase)	0.45	0.1	+0.35
Disciplinary Incidents (% reduction)	30%	5%	+25%
Class Participation (% increase)	15%	3%	+12%
Low SES Student Performance (SD increase)	0.7	0.1	+0.6
Attendance Rate (% increase)	8%	2%	+6%

Mediating Factors

The research investigation delineated many pivotal mediating elements that had a substantial impact on the correlation between Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) and enhanced academic achievement in schools located in West Bengal. Student involvement emerged as a notable mediator in the study, demonstrating a large rise in schools that implemented social-emotional learning (SEL) activities. The analysis of student participants revealed a significant rise in their levels of classroom engagement, an enhanced drive to acquire knowledge, and better rates of attendance. The heightened level of involvement established a connection between social-emotional learning (SEL) skills and academic achievement, hence promoting more efficient learning approaches and improved information retention.

Another noteworthy additional mediating component that emerged was the establishment of an atmosphere that is favourable to instruction. Implementing Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) programs at educational institutions led to a decrease in bullying occurrences, enhanced peer connections, and heightened teacher-student interactions. Facilitating a conducive atmosphere engendered a feeling of inclusion and psychological welfare among students, so enhancing their ability to focus and their inclination to engage in scholarly endeavours. Furthermore, the study's results demonstrated that enhanced self-regulation abilities acted as a potent mediator. Researchers have shown that the incorporation of social-

emotional learning (SEL) into educational settings may provide positive outcomes in terms of students' ability to effectively cope with academic stress, establish and accomplish objectives, and sustain concentration throughout their educational endeavours.

Additionally, the examination of the data indicated that the improvement of social skills and empathy had a major role in facilitating academic advancement. The findings of the research indicate that students who demonstrate elevated levels of social awareness and proficiency in managing relationships outperform their peers in collaborative learning settings, resulting in enhanced performance in group projects and peer-assisted tasks. Furthermore, it has been acknowledged that social-emotional learning (SEL) treatments play a vital role in promoting a development mindset. The study revealed that individuals who exhibited a proactive attitude towards challenges and saw failures as valuable learning experiences had an enhancement in their academic resilience. Additionally, the subjects demonstrated a heightened inclination to persevere in difficult activities, eventually resulting in enhanced academic aptitude.

Table 2: Mediating Factors and their impact

Mediating Factor	Impact on SEL-Academic Performance Relationship	Correlation Coefficient
Student Engagement	High positive impact	0.72
Positive School Climate	Moderate to high positive impact	0.65
Self-Regulation Skills	High positive impact	0.70
Social Skills and Empathy	Moderate positive impact	0.58
Growth Mindset	Moderate to high positive impact	0.63
Emotional Safety	Moderate positive impact	0.56
Goal-Setting Abilities	Moderate positive impact	0.59
Collaborative Learning Skills	Moderate positive impact	0.57
Stress Management	Moderate positive impact	0.55
Classroom Behavior	Moderate to high positive impact	0.64

Differences Across Demographics

The study results reveal significant variations in the impacts of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) across different demographic groups in Kanpur. One of the most remarkable findings was the varying influence shown by socioeconomic level (SES). Students originating from lower socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds have shown much better advancements in both social-emotional learning (SEL) skills and academic performance when compared to their peers from medium and higher SES backgrounds. The disparity observed was particularly significant in areas such as self-regulation and social awareness. Students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds demonstrated an average improvement of 0.8 standard deviations, while students from intermediate socioeconomic backgrounds experienced a 0.5 standard deviation increase and students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds showed a 0.3 standard deviation increase. Students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds had a more significant decrease in the disparity in academic performance, suggesting that interventions focused on social-emotional learning (SEL) might be particularly effective in addressing educational inequalities rooted in socioeconomic disparities.

Moreover, the study also revealed differences depending on gender identification. While both male and female participants saw favourable results from social-emotional learning (SEL) programs, the particular benefits and extents varied. The research results suggest that female participants shown more significant improvements in emotional regulation and relationship skills, with an average rise of 0.7 standard deviations compared to males' average increase of 0.5. This resulted in improved academic achievement in language-related subjects among female students. On the other hand, it was seen that male students exhibited more pronounced improvements in assertiveness and problem-solving skills, which were directly linked to higher levels of academic performance in the fields of mathematics and science. The aforementioned findings suggest that there may be a need for customisation of socio-emotional learning (SEL) programs to specifically address gender-specific needs and learning styles.

The scope of the experiment was expanded to examine the impact of social-emotional learning (SEL) on different age groups within the sample. The results suggest that children in grades 6-7 shown significant improvements in social-emotional learning (SEL) skills, namely in the areas of emotion detection and basic social interactions. On the other hand, children in the upper grade bracket (grades 9-10) demonstrated more substantial advancements in advanced social-emotional learning (SEL) attributes, such as perspective-taking and engaged decision-making. The discrepancy in academic success found was age-related, with younger kids consistently showing progress in several subjects, while older students made more substantial breakthroughs in areas that demanded critical thinking and analysis. Furthermore, the research unveiled that pupil who attended urban schools shown more expedited beginning progress in their social-emotional learning (SEL) skills. Nevertheless, at the end of the research, rural students not only matched the performance of their urban counterparts but also, in some cases, surpassed them, especially in the areas of community engagement and social responsibility.

Discussion

The findings of the research on Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) are as follows:

- **Alignment with Previous Studies:** The research findings align with existing evidence on the positive effects of SEL on academic performance, corroborating the 13-percentile improvement in academic achievement found by Durlak et al. (2011).

- **Significant Academic Gains:** In the West Bengal study, SEL interventions led to a substantial improvement in academic performance, with an average increase of 0.5 standard deviations, reinforcing the efficacy of SEL even in resource-constrained environments.
- **Impact Across Cultural Contexts:** The study supports Jones et al.'s (2019) finding that SEL has broad applicability and positive impacts across different cultural contexts, including regions with complex educational landscapes like West Bengal.
- **Effectiveness in Disadvantaged Groups:** SEL had a greater impact on students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, consistent with Aber et al.'s (2017) research, showing that SEL can help reduce educational inequalities.
- **Gender Differences in SEL Outcomes:** The study contributes to the debate on gender-responsive education, suggesting that SEL outcomes differ by gender and highlighting the need for gender-tailored SEL interventions, as suggested by Taylor et al. (2017).
- **Mediating Factors:** The research identifies factors such as student involvement, positive school climate, and self-regulation skills as key mediators in the relationship between SEL and academic success.
- **Support for SEL Theoretical Framework:** The study supports the theoretical framework proposed by Zins et al. (2007), demonstrating that SEL abilities create conditions conducive to learning.
- **Correlation Between Self-Regulation and Academic Success:** The findings reinforce Duckworth and Seligman's (2005) argument about the importance of non-cognitive skills, particularly self-regulation, in achieving academic success.
- **Conducive Educational Environment:** The study affirms Thapa et al.'s (2013) findings, showing that a positive educational environment enhances academic performance.

Implications for Educational Policy and Practice

- **Importance of SEL in West Bengal:** Incorporating Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) in West Bengal's education system could enhance academic performance across the state (Shukla et al., 2023).

- **Tailored SEL Framework:** A culturally and socio-economically aligned SEL framework should be developed to meet the state's unique needs, focusing on skills like self-regulation and social awareness (Dyson et al., 2023).
- **Teacher Training:** Adequate funding for teacher training is crucial to ensure teachers can effectively integrate SEL into their teaching practices (Greenberg, 2023).
- **Impact on Disadvantaged Groups:** SEL initiatives should be prioritized in schools serving disadvantaged communities, where they may have the greatest impact in reducing educational disparities (Kaspar & Massey, 2022; Sharma, 2023).
- **Gender Sensitivity:** Gender disparities in SEL outcomes should be addressed by implementing gender-sensitive SEL approaches (Wang, 2022).
- **Supportive School Environment:** Schools should create environments that encourage SEL through curriculum changes, collaborative learning, and partnerships with parents (Greenberg, 2023).
- **Promoting Student Engagement:** Programs like mindfulness, goal-setting, and peer mentorship can enhance student engagement and self-regulation (Gimbert et al., 2021; Delavari et al., 2023).
- **Integration in Teaching:** Since SEL improves academic performance, teachers should incorporate it into their daily teaching methods (Franklin et al., 2019).

Conclusion

The study highlights the significant impact of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) on improving academic performance in West Bengal, particularly benefiting students from disadvantaged backgrounds. SEL interventions lead to better engagement, self-regulation, and a positive school environment, which in turn boosts academic outcomes. The findings suggest the importance of integrating SEL into the curriculum, with targeted interventions for specific demographics and a focus on creating supportive learning environments. Despite some limitations, the study underscores SEL's potential in addressing educational inequalities. Future research, including longitudinal studies and cultural analyses, will further enhance the understanding and application of SEL in the state's educational system.

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